

DISTRIBUTION OF MOLECULAR WEIGHT IN BAMBOO CELLULOSES

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The celluloses of bamboo wood (*Dendrocalamus strictus*) and also three previously isolated bamboo celluloses have been nitrated, then fractionated by solution or precipitation methods. The degrees of polymerization of the fractions have been estimated by a viscometric method.

The average degrees of polymerization of the cellulose of the bamboo wood, and of the three isolated celluloses, were determined to be about 1620, 1350, 776 and 1260 respectively.

The distribution in molecular weight of the cellulose in bamboo wood, a monocotyledonal angiosperm, is found to be somewhat different from that reported in the literature for the cellulose in the gymnosperms, hemlock and spruce. Celluloses isolated from mixed species of bamboo woods show complex molecular weight distribution curves

Although there is available considerable chemical and physical evidence (Kita and Azami, *Cellulose Ind. Tokyo*, 1925, 1, 162; Oguri, *ibid.*, 1933, 9, 59; *J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, Suppl. binding, 1932, 35, 400), that the cellulose of bamboo wood is essentially similar in structure to that of cotton, no study of distribution of molecular weight of bamboo cellulose seems to have been carried out in spite of the both theoretical and practical importance (Spurlin, 'Cellulose and Cellulose Derivatives', edited by Emil Ott, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, N. Y., 1946, pp. 930—942) of this characteristic. Thus, in the present investigations the recently reported technique of Mitchell (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1946, 38, 843) has been employed with bamboo wood to determine the molecular weight distribution of its carbohydrates. Three isolated bamboo celluloses, separated from wood by various procedures, have also been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—The internode portion of an old (about ten years) culm of bamboo wood (*Dendrocalamus strictus*), nearly 25 inches in girth, was reduced to fine shavings. Three unbleached bamboo celluloses were kindly supplied to the authors from sources in India. Cellulose A (from the Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun, U. P.) was prepared from bamboo (*Dendrocalamus strictus*) by a well-controlled 'fractional digestion' procedure (Bhargava, *Indian Forest Bulletin*, 1945, No. 129) using as reagents a mixture of sodium hydroxide and sodium sulphide. Cellulose B (from Bengal Paper Mills Ltd., Raniganj, Bengal) was secured from mixed species of Indian bamboos, also by a fractional digestion treatment with an alkaline aqueous solution. Cellulose C (from India Paper Pulp Company Ltd., Naihati, Bengal) was isolated from

mixed species of Indian bamboos by acidic digestion with a 4.5% solution of magnesium bisulphite.

Nitration.—Both the bamboo wood and the celluloses were nitrated using a mixture consisting of HNO_3 (64% by weight), H_3PO_4 (26%) and P_2O_5 (10%). The methods of nitration, of stabilization, and of washing the nitrocelluloses free from nitrolignins and other non-cellulosic impurities were essentially those described by Mitchell (*loc. cit.*). Weight yields of nitrate from celluloses A, B and C were 159, 157 and 155% respectively.

Fractionation of Cellulose Nitrate.—The cellulose nitrates obtained from bamboo wood and from celluloses A and C were divided into fractions having different molecular weights by a fractional precipitation method in a water-acetone system as suggested by Zurisch (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1940, 64, 269). The nitrate of cellulose B yielded eleven fractions by a fractional solution method (Mitchell, *loc. cit.*) using appropriate solvent mixtures of ethanol (95%) and ethyl acetate.

Viscosity of Cellulose Nitrate Solutions.—Solutions of the cellulose nitrates were prepared at concentrations of 0.5 g. of nitrate per liter of C. P. ethyl acetate or C. P. acetone. The viscosity of these solutions was determined, usually at $20.5 \pm 0.1^\circ$, using Cannon-Fenske type viscometers (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1938, 10, 297). Since the viscosity of the dilute cellulose nitrate solutions tended to decrease on standing, a solution was rapidly effected and viscosities were measured without delay.

Calculation of Degree of Polymerization.—From the times of outflow from the viscometer for the pure solvent (t_0), and each cellulose nitrate solution (t), the relative viscosity (η_r), the specific viscosity (η_{sp}), the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$, and finally the degree of polymerization (D. P.) were calculated by use of the following relationships:

$$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1 = \frac{t}{t_0} - 1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$[\eta] = \frac{\eta_{sp}}{c} = \frac{1}{1 + K(\eta_{sp})} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\text{D. P.} = K [\eta] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where the concentration of nitrocellulose (c) is in g./100 c. c. of solvent.

The value of the constant "K" was determined graphically for a particular cellulose nitrate-solvent system by plotting (η_{sp}/c) against (η_{sp}) for different concentrations as suggested by Huggins (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1943, 35, 982). These plots were found to be linear. The ratio of the slope to intercept in these plots, at the point of zero concentration, gave the value of "K". It was found to vary from 0.312 to 0.350 for cellulose nitrate in ethyl acetate, depending upon

temperature and the extent and nature of impurities associated with the polymer. The constant K was taken as 100 (cf. Mitchell, *loc. cit.*).

An average degree of polymerization was calculated for the unfractionated celluloses from data secured from the several fractions by use of the relationship

$$\text{D. P. (Ave.)} = \frac{\sum(w) (\text{D. P.})}{\sum(w)}$$

where w is the weight of a particular fraction and "D. P." is its degree of polymerization.

TABLE I
Study of nitration of bamboo cellulose B.*

Expt. No.	Amount of cellulose.	Time of nitration.	Percentage** yield.	η_{sp} †	‡ Average D. P.
I	4.375 g.	20 hrs.	143.5	0.482	818
II	4.375	6	150.2	0.500	845
III	4.875	4	151.0	0.530	882
IV	8.750	6	157.2	0.517	877
V	8.750	2	155.0	0.488	820
VI	8.750	0.5	157.1	0.521	875

* In all cases nitration was conducted at $20 \pm 0.5^\circ$ using 850. g. of the nitrating acids.

** Calculated on air-dry basis. The nitrates from all experiments were completely soluble in ethyl acetate.

† Efflux time with C. P. ethyl acetate at 25° —230 min., η_{sp} is for 0.05% solution in ethyl acetate at 25° .

‡ Taking $K=100$ and $K'=0.85$.

TABLE II
Fractionation of nitrocellulose from bamboo wood.*

Fraction number.	Cumulative amount of water added.	Wt. of fraction.	Cumulative wt ppted.	**Efflux time for viscosity.	† D. P.
I	51.0 c.c.	0.2108 g.	15.92 %	6.75 min.	2328
II	83.0	0.1440	26.78	5.92	2080
III	76.0	0.1895	41.04	6.34	1805
IV	100.0	0.2781	62.06	5.05	1680
V	125.0	0.1512	73.48	4.78	1550
VI	150.0	0.1250	82.89	4.25	1385
VII	175.0	0.0380	85.78	3.70	975
VIII	200.0	0.0758	91.50	3.28	710
IX‡	Not. ppted.	0.1124	100.00	2.95	482

Total 1.3248

* Total amount of material used for fractionation by precipitation at 24° was 1.3281g. in 425 c.c. solution.

** Efflux time is for 0.05% solution in C. P. ethyl acetate at 20.50° . Efflux time for C. P. ethyl acetate itself was 2.34 min.

† D. P. was calculated using value of $K'=0.83$ and $K=100$,

‡ Last fraction obtained by evaporation of the solution to dryness on a water-bath.

TABLE III

Fractionation of nitrocellulose from bamboo cellulose A.*

Fraction number.	Cumulative amount of water added.	Wt. of fraction.	Cumulative wt. ppted.	**Efflux time for viscosity.	†D. P.
I	36.0 c.c.	0.0826 g.	5.80%	6.62 min.	2205
II	37.0	0.1281	14.80	6.31	2100
III	42.0	0.2340	31.25	5.74	1892
IV	49.0	0.2985	52.07	6.17	1655
V	53.0	0.1592	63.24	4.86	1416
VI	63.0	0.1515	73.87	4.37	1220
VII	72.0	0.0676	77.91	3.54	802
VIII	83.0	0.0899	80.71	3.28	635
IX	95.0	0.0462	83.96	3.03	479
X	115.0	0.0986	90.88	2.38	358
XI‡	Not ppted.	0.1310	100.00	2.50	165
Total 1.4252					

* Total amount of material used for fractionation by precipitation at 22°—1.4266 g. in 820 c.c. solution.

** Efflux time is for 0.05% solutions in C. P. ethyl acetate at 20.5°, efflux time for C. P. ethyl acetate itself was 2.42 min.

† D. P. was calculated on the basis of $K=100$ and $K'=0.33$.

‡ Last fraction obtained by evaporation of solution to dryness on a water-bath.

TABLE IV

Fractionation of nitrocellulose from bamboo cellulose B.*

Fraction number	Solvent mixture composition* †		Weight of fraction.	Cumulated wt. dissolved.	††Efflux time.	‡D. P.
	Ethyl alcohol†	Ethyl acetate.				
I	100.00	0.0	0.1600 g.	1.55%	2.85 min.	22
II	70.00	30.0	0.1490	2.99	2.35	48
III	60.00	40.0	0.0535	3.39	2.56	217
IV	50.00	50.0	0.3845	7.12	3.12	632
V	45.00	55.0	1.2885	19.57	3.21	697
VI	42.00	58.0	1.7521	36.57	3.25	723
VII	40.00	60.0	1.1459	47.64	3.27	735
VIII	37.00	63.0	1.6350	63.44	3.40	820
IX	35.00	65.0	1.7008	79.86	3.48	870
X	32.00	68.0	1.4932	94.31	3.58	930
XI	30.00	70.0	0.5618	100.00	3.64	966

*Total amount of material used for fractionation by solution method at 25°—10.0 g.

**Composition is by volume.

†85% ethyl alcohol was used.

†† Efflux time is for 0.05% solution in C. P. ethyl acetate at 25° except for fraction I, for which it is for 0.1% solution.

‡D. P. was calculated using $K'=0.35$ and $K=100$.

TABLE V

Fractionation of nitrocellulose from bamboo cellulose C.*

Fraction number.	Cumulative amount of water added.	Weight of fraction.	Cumulative wt. ppted.	**Efflux time for viscosity.	†D. P.
I	38.0 c. c.	0.2036 g.	14.85%	3.66 min.	1890
II	39.0	0.0680	19.73	3.52	1795
III	41.0	0.0975	26.73	3.39	1705
IV	43.0	0.1605	38.38	3.14	1512
V	46.0	0.1237	47.26	3.00	1380
VI	49.0	0.1434	57.56	2.89	1285
VII	54.0	0.1112	65.77	2.85	1245
VIII	60.0	0.1810	79.09	2.82	1215
IX	70.0	0.1055	86.68	2.31	587
X	100.0	0.0530	90.48	2.20	416
XI‡	Not ppted.	0.1823	100.00	2.08	110
		<u>1.3924</u>			

*Total amount of material used for fractionation by precipitation at 22°=1.8720 g. in 320 c. c. of solution.

**Efflux time is for 0.05% solution in C. P. acetone at 20.5°. Efflux time for C. P. acetone at 20.5° was 1.97 min.

†D. P. was calculated on basis of $K=100$ and $K'=0.468$.

‡Last fraction obtained by evaporation of the solution to dryness on a water bath.

DISCUSSION

Since Berl and Rueff (*Cellulosechem.*, 1931, 12, 53; 1933, 14, 115) showed that cellulose could be nitrated and renitrated without appreciable depolymerization by use of a nitrating mixture containing phosphoric acid and phosphorous pentoxide but no sulphuric acid, a readily carried out method has been at hand whereby cellulose can be converted into a soluble nitrate amenable to molecular weight distribution studies by use of well-known techniques for fractionation and for molecular weight determination.

To secure undegraded and yet completely soluble cellulose nitrates, however, the nitrating reaction must be properly conducted. Thus, in the present investigation, cellulose B was nitrated under a number of reaction conditions and for each cellulose nitrate prepared its weight-yield, solubility in ethyl acetate, and its average degree of polymerization were determined (Table I). Since all nitrates were entirely soluble in ethyl acetate, the reaction conditions giving the highest degree of polymerization (*i. e.* Expt. VI) were those chosen and used in subsequent work with the isolated bamboo celluloses. Bamboo wood was nitrated using Mitchell's conditions (*loc. cit.*).

The weight-yield of cellulose nitrate obtained from bamboo wood was 91.2%, calculated on an extractive-free basis. With hemlock wood Mitchell (*loc. cit.*) obtained a yield of 120–130% under identical conditions, while for pure cellulose the yield should be 180%. Extractive-free bamboo wood

(*Dendrocalamus strictus*) has been reported to contain on the average 64% of Cross and Bevan cellulose (cf. Bhargava, *loc. cit.*). Had all this cellulose in the bamboo wood been recovered as cellulose nitrate, the weight-yield expected is about 115%. The deviation of the actual yield from this theoretical value suggests that some of the carbohydrates in bamboo wood, which are isolated as Cross and Bevan cellulose, differ in characteristics from those in hemlock. The yields secured on nitration of the isolated bamboo celluloses were also found to be less than those anticipated from theory.

The nitrates obtained from bamboo wood, and from celluloses A and C were fractionated by the precipitation procedure of Zurisch (*loc. cit.*), in preference to the solution method of Mitchell (*loc. cit.*) used earlier with the nitrate of cellulose B, because the latter technique was time consuming and since gelatinization occurred which gave rise to difficulty in separating liquid and solid phases. With Zurisch's method, the extent of precipitation at a particular state of the system was found to be quite reproducible. The average degree of polymerization of the celluloses in several fractions was estimated by viscometric procedures.

By integration of the fractionation data (Table II), the average degree of polymerization of the celluloses from bamboo wood was calculated to be about 1620, which corresponds to a molecular weight of about 260,000. This is considerably less than Mitchell's (*loc. cit.*) average value of 2000 found for the carbohydrates of Western hemlock wood (*Tsuga heterophylla*), but higher than that of Atchison (*Paper Trade J.*, 1943, 116, No. 22, 23-34) of 1450 for holocellulose from spruce wood (*Picea mariana*).

However, with respect to distribution of molecular weights (Fig. 1), the celluloses of hemlock (Mitchel, *loc. cit.*) and spruce (Atchison, *loc. cit.*)

FIG. 1

woods are about entirely either of rather high (more than 2000) or else quite low (less than 500) degree of polymerization, with intermediate celluloses being

present only in small proportion. On the other hand, nearly 65% of the cellulose from the bamboo wood are found to be of intermediate degree of polymerization (500 to 2000), with only about 10 and 26% being of lower and higher, respectively. Two maxima in frequency of distribution are observed in the higher range. Molecular weight distribution difference between the carbohydrates or cellulose of bamboo and those of hemlock and spruce may arise because of differences in botanical characteristics of hemlock and spruce as gymnosperms, compared to bamboo as a monocotyledonal angiosperm.

Isolation of cellulose from woods by use of aqueous solutions of alkaline or acidic reagents to accomplish delignification usually is accompanied by the dissolving into the aqueous reagent solutions of some low molecular weight carbohydrates; thereby the average molecular weight of the remaining isolated cellulose tends to be higher than that of the total carbohydrates originally present in the wood. This isolation procedure simultaneously tends to depolymerize the carbohydrates and may alter them in other ways. Both tendencies will be reflected in the distribution of molecular weights in isolated celluloses. Fractionation data for cellulose A is given in Table III. The differential

FIG. 2

distribution curve found for bamboo wood carbohydrates compared with that for cellulose A (Fig. 1), both from *Dendrocalamus strictus*, shows a general

shifting of the curve to somewhat lower levels in degree of polymerization as might be expected from hydrolytic influences acting during the isolation reaction. This trend is affirmed by the average degree of polymerization of about 1350 found for isolated cellulose A compared with that of about 1620 found for the cellulose of bamboo wood. Bamboo cellulose B appears to have been markedly reduced in average molecular weight in the course of its isolation from mixed species of bamboos under alkaline conditions (D. P. = 775), while the acidic conditions of delignifications used to secure Cellulose C did not yield serious decrease in degree of polymerization (D. P. = 1260). The complex trends in the integral molecular weight distribution curves for cellulose B and C (Fig. 2) are probably to be traced to the fact that mixed species of bamboo wood were used for preparation of these celluloses.

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